

An “ideal” Daycare Centre for People with Dementia: reflections and suggestions

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ABSTRACT The Daycare Centre “Le Civette” in Florence enrolls subjects with an intermediate/severe entity of cognitive decline. With the aim to reduce the caregiver’s burden, the staff applies emotion-oriented therapy creating interest and pleasure in the subjects, so that they want to attend the structure every day. The assistance which includes adequate social psychology affects the progressive evolution of cognitive and behavioural decline. We stress the importance of the patient’s role as a subject in a relationship, and not an object of study, observation and measures. For instance, it has been underlined the importance of maintaining a conversation alive even if the meaning is lost: the pleasure of conversation can remain even if the language gets damaged, so the feeling of “exclusion” is reduced to minimal levels. Therefore, the ideal daycare centre is the place where the attendee is evaluated not only for his defective symptoms, but also as a person longing for attention and appreciation.

KEYWORDS dementia, day-care center

Introduction

In a recent Congress, we examined some critical aspects that are often found in Alzheimer Daycare Centres. [1] In this article, on the contrary, we would like to focus on the positive functions and, above all, to outline the qualities an ideal Daycare Centre for people with dementia (PWD) should have. The purposes of a daycare centre organised for this clinical situation are well known:

1. Severity and frequency decrease of patient’s BPSD (Behavioural Psychological Symptoms Dementia), especially those noxious to themselves and those around them. In Italy, the presence of BPSD constitutes one of the most important motivations justifying the allocation of a patient to a daycare centre.
2. respecting and supporting residual cognitive and functional

abilities, to avoid disempowerment, namely a dependence not corresponding to the patient’s real capabilities.

3. reducing the social isolation of PWD and their family.
4. delaying residential institutionalisation.
5. decreasing incongruent hospitalisation.
6. counselling formal or informal caregivers, listening to them, providing.
7. information and training.
8. opening social exchanges between DCC and the community.

The Daycare Centre “Le Civette” Design

The Daycare Centre “Le Civette” in Florence belongs to the National Health Service who is responsible for the daycare financing. The centre accepts subjects with an intermediate/severe entity of cognitive decline, for whom applying a cognitive oriented therapy is not possible and counterproductive for BPSD decrease.

In this Daycare Centre, therefore, we work essentially with emotion-oriented therapy, with the aim of reducing the caregiver’s psychological and physical burden creating interest and

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pleasure in the subjects, so that they want to attend the structure every day. This objective is usually obtained through the combination of the right staff, a suitable environment and the correct choice of offered activities.

The service personnel includes 7 healthcare assistants, 1 nurse, 2 educators, 1 music therapist, 1 art therapist, 1 neurologist and 1 psycho-geriatrician. For the staff, the compulsory qualities are experience, tolerance and empathy: the environment has to be prosthetic, residential, familiar, constant and simple, namely easy to spend time in. According to M. Jones the activities have to be ecological, one step, with low unsuccessful possibilities, without abstract conceptualisation, gratifying, respecting the premorbid competences and hobbies, based therefore on spontaneity and on maintaining personal identity. Examples of such activities are music therapy, art therapy, kitchen therapy, occupational therapy, doll therapy, reminiscence therapy, gardening and walking. An adequate combination of staff qualities, environment and programmes produce exciting results on quality of life for subjects who spend ten hours, six days a week, in a daycare centre [2-3].

The Staff/Client Relationship (Therapeutic roles)

As T. Kitwood stated the progressive evolution of cognitive and behavioural decline is indemnified by what he defines as adequate social psychology, whose most important component is the quality of Assistance [4].

In this article, considering our psycho-geriatric background, we would like to stress the importance of safeguarding the quality of assistance, and the importance of the patient's role as a subject in a relationship, and not as an object of study, observation and measures. We believe our patients have many needs both basic such as supervision, assistance in daily living activities, drugs administration, reactivation programmes, and psychological, for example, the attachment, inclusion, reassurance and encouragement to keep occupied.

Unfortunately, when treating PWD, very little is said about staff-patient verbal and friendly relationships. The reasons for this are easily understandable; our patients are in a situation of cognitive decline, the language is poor, often not logical or understandable, body language very often substitutes the verbal communication. So in a daycare centre, the staff considers themselves as the healthy part, whereas regular attendees are automatically the sick ones: it's easier to order, to organize, to evaluate, to not allow and to control rather than judging the patient as a person, as an equal [5].

It's necessary to find a different approach between staff and patients, based on a "double unspeakable belief": "I know you are sick, you know I am healthy, but I can help you" and "You know I am sick, but you know I also have some part of me in order". The latter patient's imaginary thought refers to an emotion processing, which reflects a well functioning activity even in severely demented patients. Therefore many of them try to establish a friendship with some members of staff. Such members appear, in the eyes of a patient, as the most gentle, the best listeners, the ablest to understand verbal and non-verbal messages, the most seriously involved in a communication with a person, even if in an odd one, as often occurs in this pathology.

This happens mainly when the patient chooses the operator, based on their empathetic ability. We are not the ones who choose the patient but is the patient who chooses us as their most important caregivers. The patient has noticed the possibility of having a reassuring, holding but not a coercive relationship with

a particular subject. This subject has shown his ability to use not only verbal communication, but also body language, which is essential for our patients, as well as the prosody, the proxemics, the correct eye contact, the physical touch, and respecting their time limits. Therefore one of the purposes of a daycare centre's coordinator will be to help the operator become the patient's communication therapist. The first important aspect of this therapeutic role is to hold the patient in a relationship, for the most extended period possible.

Managing Conversation and the Speech/Oral Dimension

We know that a critical component of the relationship is speech and we know that some authors consider dementia an oral communication disease. Speech has to be cured, and the cure is done with words. In subjects affected by severe dementia vocabulary is limited, not connected to the appropriate terminologies, therefore other words often very far from the intended are used.

Communication becomes difficult, and both patient and interlocutor become disappointed causing the patient to speak less and less, as well as the interlocutor also addressing them to a lesser degree. This contributes to progressive patient isolation, which increasingly damages them and worsens their disease, as well as causing an unpleasant feeling of inability on the part of the caregiver. However, if communication declines very quickly, the conversation gets damaged, but the pleasure can remain so that some authors suggest the importance of maintaining a conversation alive even if the meaning is lost [6].

This aspect has to be implemented in an ideal daycare centre as if we can maintain a certain interest in the conversation, even when the patient's words are deeply damaged, the relationship is kept alive, the cognitive decline is slower, and essentially the patient lives a positive experience. The target is, therefore, to activate a possible conversation, where it's necessary to respect a conversational courtesy. When the patient is speaking I keep silent listening to them, and when they have finished speaking I try to understand something from the chaos of their words, and I give back, in my words, what I believe to have understood. So the patient can pick up a word and continue speaking. This procedure, where objective remarks by PWD are combined with subjective cues by the caregiver, can create a new style of speaking and keep the patient in a conversation, even not meaningful, but of great importance. This contributes to a passage from object to subject as mentioned previously.

Empowering Social Relationship at DCC

We must remember in our social context the patient comes to a daycare centre after having spent many years with their family, where he built a significant relationship with one selected family member. Sometimes this member is the wife, husband, son or daughter. The daycare centre, therefore, has to replicate this symbiotic relationship with a selected representative.

We must remember moreover that it is, not always but very frequently, trying to stay in a group, even if little, for subjects affected by severe dementia. For example, we usually come across these problems in a triadic group, whereas in a favourable context patients are oriented to establishing a dyadic relationship. This separation, from a familiar attachment to a daycare centre connection, must be very slow, nearly imperceptible; it's very important to organize an adequate period of co-attendance before the family member is no longer present. So the feeling of "exclusion", which is one of the features of dementia philosophy

(exclusion from the working world, from production, from social relationships...) is reduced to minimal levels, primarily when the therapist can use his epistemophilic and empathetic skills. DCC staff must have natural capacities and motivations which are part of their psychological traits, such as empathy and solidarity, including the ability to recognise, when a patient spends a lot of time with them and therefore exceeding their attention span, as a successful outcome.

The true instrument the staff must have is an internal therapeutic project to be active participators. The operator must feel the desire to observe and better understand what is behind PWD behaviour, and finally to engage the PWD in a relationship, both verbal and non-verbal, resulting congruence between them. In this case, it is often possible to change a relationship in which the essential components are "I" and "you" into another one where the principal subject is "we". This usually happens when the member of staff is capable of privileging the visual and manual or tactile channel over the verbal one. When this happens the daycare centre becomes a place where every patient brings the complex structure of his cognitive and emotional setting, with their healthy and sick parts, and, above all, where it's possible, the Daycare Centre must organize an alternative field compared to pathological one, in which it's possible to evaluate and to expand well functioning areas of a patient. Here it's possible for him to express himself and carry out wishes, continue old hobbies or find new ones. Doing so the daycare centre can promote the retrieval of pre-existing abilities and interests, both real, (such as grooming, cooking, gardening...) and illusory. The latter situation involves, for example, taking care of a doll, sometimes the doll is a son or daughter, sometimes a grandchild, sometimes an unprotected little boy who the patient looks after, denying his frailty. It is critical to recuperate a highly invested aspect of the past, such as parenthood-grandparenthood, or some personality traits, such as the intolerance of dependency. Of course, this past aspect can come to life again, due to an intuitive feeling or to a defence mechanism, proceeding, in this way, the patient continues to express his own identity. For this reason, the ideal daycare centre is the place where the attendee is evaluated not only for his defective symptoms but also as a person longing for attention and appreciation.

References

1. Gori G., Marsili A. Quali sono i limiti di un Centro Diurno Alzheimer? 8th Congresso Nazionale sui CDAlzheimer. Pistoia, 16/6/2017).
2. Jones, M. Gentlecare. Changing the experience of Alzheimer disease in a positive way. Hartley & Marks Publishers Inc., 1999.
3. Gori G., Brandini P., Piccininni MS, et al. Il centro Diurno Alzheimer "Le Civette", Firenze. I luoghi della cura. Anno XII-N.3, CIC Edizioni Internazionali, 2014.
4. Kitwood T. Dementia Reconsidered: The person comes first. Open University Press, 1997.
5. Reichmann R. I Centri Diurni per psicotici. I quaderni dell'ARPA. Giornata di Studio, Casa della Cultura, Milano, 28/9/2002.
6. Vigorelli P. La conversazione possibile con il malato Alzheimer. Franco Angeli, srl, Milano, 2004.